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mEducator: Multi type content sharing and repurposing in medical education

Iolie Nicolaidou¹, Panagiotis Bamidis², Athos Antoniadis¹, Maria Nikolaidou²,
Constantinos Pattichis¹, Daniela Giordano³

¹ Department of Computer Science, University of Cyprus

² Lab of Medical Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

³ Dipartimento di Ingegneria Informatica e Telecomunicazioni, Università di Catania
iolie.nicolaidou@cut.ac.cy, bamidis@med.auth.gr, athos@cs.ucy.ac.cy, mnikol@med.auth.gr
pattichi@cs.ucy.ac.cy, dgiordan@diit.unict.it

Abstract: The problem that the mEducator Best Practice Network (BPN) endeavors refers to the abundance of medical educational content in individual EU academic institutions, which is not widely available or easy to retrieve due to the lack of standardized content sharing mechanisms. The mEducator BPN aims to implement and critically evaluate existing standards and reference models in the field of e-learning in order to enable specialized state-of-the-art medical educational content to be discovered, retrieved, shared and re-used across European institutions. The project currently focuses on the development of two contemporary ways of achieving content sharing, a solution based on Web2.0 technologies and a solution based on Semantic Web Services. These solutions will be compared and tested with users. The resulting solutions will address the needs of different types of users, such as students, educators, doctors and health professionals and they will be easily transferable to other domains and disciplines.

Introduction

Medical academic institutions and medical professional societies alike are increasingly required to invest in external overspecialised expertise in order to enrich their curricula or their educational material by developing overspecialized courses and corresponding educational content. Such content is difficult, at the moment, to be discovered, retrieved, re-used and thus shared across institutions and among medical teachers and students (undergraduate and professionals alike). The new opportunities offered by the expansion of information and communication technology (ICT) have enabled the explosion of online education and e-learning.

Collaboration and content sharing (i.e. virtual expert educator sharing) in medical education will inevitably alter the overall process of developing and preparing course materials. But, the notion of collaboration goes beyond merely sharing tasks and content across different educators. Shared resources should be making use of educational standards for the interoperable use of medical educational material across Europe in order to maximize content uptake by medical educators in attempting to underpin and extend current teaching and learning, minimize inefficient practice, reduce costs, and eventually improve the consistency and quality of health care and wellbeing of patients throughout the EU (Bamidis et al., 2008).

Today, an increasing number of higher academic institutions are using a variety of web-based learning management tools to support their teaching. This gained experience indicates that similar web-based tools can support and enhance educational collaboration on a permanent basis among higher education and research institutions in medicine. Developers of e-learning around the world point out that access to comprehensive repositories of learning objects (LOs) and metadata is the crucial factor in the future of e-learning.

Statement of the problem

There is an abundance of medical educational content available in individual EU academic institutions. However, this is not widely available or easy to discover and retrieve, due to the lack of standardized content sharing mechanisms. Although a lot of effort has been put in the area of educational content development, description, and sharing, currently there is no prominent clear and standards-based solution for the seamless sharing of educational content in medicine and in general, despite the fact that a number of research projects are already dealing with the exchange of learning objects (LOs). The mEducator BPN works towards this direction to provide a reference model for medical educational content sharing, retrieval and re-use based on educational standards in the field of e-learning and standardized commonplace technology.

mEducator scope and objectives

mEducator aims to examine to what extent: a) existing standards for the description of educational material can address all the possible types of medical educational material listed above, and make respective recommendations for standards extensions, b) existing standards for educational material packaging and exchange among learning management systems are adequate to support state-of-the art educational content sharing in medicine and provide respective recommendations for standards extensions, and c) a recently proposed standard-based reference model for automated educational content discovery, retrieval and sharing can be deployed for medical educational content delivery and sharing and whether extensions are required.

More specifically, the goals of mEducator are to:

- a) identify and collect a critical mass of different types of health educational material such as:
 - conventional educational content types: lecture notes, books, lecture presentations, exam questions, practices, scientific papers, graphs, images/videos, algorithms and simulators
 - educational content types unique in medical education: teaching files, virtual patients, evidence based medicine forms, objective standard clinical examinations, clinical guidelines, anatomical atlases, digital graphical annotation and tracing of images, etc
 - alternative educational content types: active learning techniques and problem/case based learning sessions via web 2.0 technologies, serious games (2D/3D), web traces, wikis, blogs/discussion forums, etc.
- b) examine to what extend existing standards are adequate to support the packaging and seamless delivery of all types of health educational material listed above, and make respective recommendations for standards extensions.
- c) examine possible extensions of existing taxonomies, vocabularies and ontological schemata, which describe the semantics of LOs
- d) communicate and interact with standardization bodies like MedBiquitous Europe, IEEE, IMS, CEN, Health On the Net, HL7, etc to ensure adoption of recommendations/extensions into standards.

In order to derive best practices for medical educational content re-use and sharing, the mEducator BPN needs a critical mass of medical educational content types (rather than items). The educational content covers and represents the whole range of medical educational content, from traditional instructional teaching to active learning and experiential teaching/studying approaches. It spans the whole range of types, from text to exam sheets, algorithms, teaching files, computer programs (simulators or games) and interactive objects (like virtual patients and graphically traced and annotated anatomies), while it covers a variety of topics. Moreover, by taking advantage of active learning techniques and Web2.0 technologies, mEducator makes use of the user-

generated content which offers great educational value, as stand-alone educational resources bringing forward common mistakes and good practices.

Figure 1: Examples of some of the types of content that mEducator covers

mEducator has been working closely with the MedBiquitous Europe standardization body so as to adopt and implement MedBiquitous technology standards for medical and healthcare education in order to make medical content interoperable and shareable across the European Union.

The consortium has also been intensively researching the notion of repurposing of educational resources, and has adopted a set of content repurposing contexts and their definitions. The procedure for repurposing medical educational content in general can be complex and may vary greatly from one repurposing case to another, and one of the project goals is to define the best practices and procedures for content repurposing of each type.

As a BPN, mEducator attempts to compare two contemporary ways of achieving this content sharing, namely, a solution based on Web2.0 technologies, and a solution based on Semantic Web Services, as described in the following section.

In progress work: mEducator solutions

To support their teaching, institutions often use a variety of web-based Learning Content Management Systems (LCMSs) and educational standards which are developed and adopted to enable the universal description of educational content, namely, IEEE Learning Object Metadata (LOM), and SCORM (Buendia & Hervas, 2006). Current e-learning research indicates that access to comprehensive repositories of learning objects and metadata is the crucial factor in the future of e-learning and the vision of interoperability. There is a need therefore for an efficient brokerage mechanism for educational content sharing. The mEducator project has reached consensus of partners and stakeholders and has produced a metadata scheme for educational material containing properties that describe not only the resource itself but also the educational aspects (such as

educational objectives, learning outcomes, pedagogical models, assessment methods). The produced metadata scheme is related to controlled vocabularies. Users' experiences in metadata creation and users' perceptions with regard to the wider notion of metadata descriptions and use have been elicited within focus groups while trying to finalize the scheme. The aim was to identify possible problems and concerns, so as to take them into account when (a) updating the schema, (b) implementing the schema in the solutions and (c) constructing suitable metadata editors. Therefore, the implementation of the scheme has recently introduced the creation of an OWL ontology for medical educational content repurposing and sharing, which is being used by the two sharing and repurposing solutions of mEducator.

The first solution being implemented within mEducator develops a brokerage mechanism based on RSS feeds, "mashup" technology and other Web 2.0 technologies. It is based on the MEDTING technology (<http://medting.com>) that allows the exchange of clinical cases, medical images and videos, which also features the MEDTING Connectors technology that allows content to be shared among other websites. This solution assumes independent and isolated content repositories (such as LCMSs) on the web and uses mashup technologies for accessing content from external websites, thus creating a loosely coupled LCMS network. Social networking functionalities have been integrated and RSS technology is employed to add user generated content as per the Health2.info best practice initiative (<http://health20.org>).

The second solution being implemented in mEducator is a sharing platform using the Semantic Web and its most recent development, the Linked Data approach: LCMSs and repositories from different physical locations, having heterogeneous access interfaces (through SOAP services or SPARQL end points) can be connected in a single access point for user content sharing. This implementation builds upon a service-oriented application framework based on the Semantic Web Services-oriented e-learning architecture (Dietze, Gugliotta & Domingue, 2008) developed as part of the LUISA project (<http://www.luisa-project.eu>) which was updated and improved to reflect on mEducator-specific requirements as well as the emerging Linked Data and Linked Services (Pedrinaci & Domingue, 2010) paradigms. As such, this solution fundamentally exploits semantic representations of data and services to provide interoperability between e-learning repositories spread across the Web.

Both mEducator solutions are currently in their beta-version and they will be tested by the target user groups of the project such as students, educators, and health professionals. mEducator currently focuses on the finalization of the mEducator ontology and the evaluation and final customizations on the two sharing solutions. Provision of the material to non-partner institutes is planned with the foreseen (sustainability) aim to invite more institutes in the distributed pool and enable content sharing across all educational institutions, regardless of whether they are mEducator consortium partners or not. Nevertheless, the consortium having received consultation from experts in the Intellectual Property sector, has established recommendations regarding the licensing scheme that enables the use of Open Educational Resources (OER), (Habler 2009, Atkins, Brown, & Hammond, 2007). The Creative Commons licensing model proposed advocates a global culture of learning and a rapidly evolving, knowledge-based world.

Future work

The mEducator BPN is expected to be completed by May 2012. Key transferable outcomes of the mEducator BPN include:

- A metadata scheme for the description of all types of medical educational content, with reference to relevant standards combining folksonomies and taxonomies (Bamidis, Kaldoudi & Pattichis, 2009) and repurposing histories ontology (Giordano, Faro, Maiorana, Pino & Spampinato, 2009) as well as relevant editors
- Recommendations on best practices in implementing and using standardized commonplace technology and respective reference models for medical educational content use, re-use and sharing.

- Technologies for medical educational content discovery and retrieval covering a vast medical educational content of a great variety of types, formally described, re-purposed and delivered along existing standards in loosely coupled isolated LCMSs and in federated LCMSs of the partners.
- A simple Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) scheme for educational content provided and re-purposed in academic networks.

The latest developments of the project can be followed at the project website (<http://www.meducator.net/>).

Partners of mEducator

The partners of mEducator are:

1	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki <i>Project Coordinator</i>	GR					
2	University of Cyprus	CY					
3	Democritus University of Thrace	GR					
4	MEDTING LTD	IR					
5	Technical University of Cluj-Napoca	RO					
6	Université Nice Sophia Antipolis	FR					
7	Medical University Plovdiv	BG					

Figure 2: The mEducator partners

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